

ACINO

Application-Centric IP/optical
Network Orchestration

ACINO / D6.2

Data Management Plan

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Revision and history chart

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Summary

Producing the Data Management Plan (DMP) within the project is a part of the Horizon 2020 pilot action on open access to research data in which ACINO participates. The purpose of the DMP is to describe the main elements of the data management policy that will be used by the ACINO project with regard to all the datasets to be generated by the project.

In other words, the Data Management Plan will describe the format and the way to store, archive and share the data created within the project as well as the use of the plan itself by the project participants. The data may include, but not limited to, code, publications as well as measured data, for example, from field trials. The Plan is a living document whose content concerning the data management is updated from its creation (month 6 of the project) to the end of the project (month 36).

1 Introduction

Following the EC template, the data management plan includes the following major components.

Figure 1. Structure (template) of the data management plan.

Specifically, for ACINO these components are summarized below.

Figure 2. Main components of the ACINO data management plan.

Details for each component are given in the following sections.

2 Data set reference and name

The following structure is proposed for ACINO data set identifier:

ACINO [Name] [Type] [Place] [Date] [Owner] [Target User]

Where

- “Name” is a short name for the data.
- “Type” describes the type of data (e.g. code, publication, measured data).
- “Place” describe the place the data were produced.
- “Data” is the date in format “YYYY-MM-DD”.
- “Owner” are the owner or owners of the data (if exist)
- [Optional] “Target user” is the target audience of the data.
- “_” (underscore) is used as the separator between the fields.

For example,

“ACINO_Field trial_Measurement_data_Kista_2015-06-30_Acreo_Internal.dat” is a data file from the field trial in Kista, Sweden from 2015-06-30 made and owned by Acreo with extension .dat (MATLAB). More information about the data is provided in the metadata (see the following section).

All the data fields in the identifier above, apart from the target user, are mandatory. If owner cannot be specified, “Unspecified-owner” should be indicated.

3 Data set description and metadata

The previous section defined a data set identifier. The data set description is essentially an expanded description of the identifier with more details.

The data set description is organized as the metadata in the similar way as the identifier but with more details and, depending on the file format, will be either incorporated as a part of the file or as a separate file (in its simplest form) in the text format. In the case of the separate metadata file, it will have the same name with suffix “METADATA”.

For example, the metadata file name for the data file from the previous section will look as follows:

“ACINO_Field trial_Measurement data_Kista_015-06-30_Acreo_Internal_METADATA.txt”

The Metadata file can also describe a number of files (e.g. a number of log files).

The project may consider a possibility to provide the metadata in XML or JSON formats, if necessary for convenience of parsing and further processing.

4 Data sharing

ACINO has chosen zenodo.org repository for storing the project data and an ACINO project account has been created¹. Zenodo.org is a repository supported by CERN and the EU OpenAire project², is open, free, searchable and structured with flexible licensing allowing for storing all types of data: datasets, images, presentations, publications and software. In addition to that,

- The repository has backup and archiving capabilities.
- The repository allows for integration github.com³ where the project code will be stored. GitHub provides a free and flexible tool for code developing and storage.
- Zenodo assigns all publicly available uploads a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make the upload easily- and uniquely-citable.

All the above makes Zenodo a good candidate as a *unified* repository for all foreseen project data (presentations, publications, code and measurement data) from ACINO.

Information on using Zenodo by the project partners with application to the ACINO data will be circulated within the consortium and addressed within the respective workpackage (WP6).

The process of making the ACINO data public and publishable at the repository will follow the procedures described in the Consortium Agreement. For the code, the project partners will follow the internal “Open Source Management Process” document.

All the public data of the project will be openly accessible at the repository. Non-public data will be archived at the repository using the “closed access” option.

¹ Zenodo.org

² openaire.eu

³ GitHub.org

5 Archiving and preservation

The Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020 require defining procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data and backup.

The zenodo.org repository possesses these archiving capabilities including backup and will be used to archive and preserve the ACINO data.

6 Use of the Data Management plan within the project

The plan is used by the ACINO partners as a reference for data management (naming, providing metadata, storing and archiving) within the project each time new project data are produced.

The project partners are introduced to the DMP and its use as part of WP6 activities. Relevant questions from partners will also be addressed within WP6. The workpackage will also provide support to the project partners on using Zenodo as the data management tool.

7 List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
XML	Extensible Markup Language